

INVESTIGATING PERFORMANCE DETERMINANTS OF LISTED COMMERCIAL BANKS IN CHINA

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to conduct an empirical investigation of the factors that determined the levels of performance of 14 commercial banks in China that were publicly traded over a period of ten years. In order to accomplish this goal, in the first place, the financial performance measurement index (PI) is built utilizing CAMEL's components. This is done as a supplement to conventional performance measurements such as ROA and ROE, and it addresses the constraints of those metrics. After PI is used to determine the performance of the banks, the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) model is used to analyze the impact of financial institution, financial, or macroeconomic on the banks' performance. Research shows the bank-specific variables have such a major impact on bank performance and therefore are key factors in the performance of Chinese-named commercial banks. Microeconomic factors have shown a considerable negative effect on bank performance whereas financial factors have shown no affect on Chinese commercial banks. This study not only presents data but also makes suggestions for how Chinese commercial bank management and banking authorities can enhance the performance of their institutions based on the findings.

Keywords: Chinese commercial banks, performance determinants, CAMELS, structural equation model

1. Introduction

A major role is played by commercial banks in the financial system of the modern economy, which serves as the modern economy's central nervous system. As the main intermediaries in the financial system, banks are vital for efficient credit allocation, sustainable and stable economic growth, and financial inclusion (Kidwell et al., 2016). China's commercial banking sector has been undergoing slow but significant reforms in tandem with the country's ongoing internationalization and economic development (Borst and Lardy, 2015). The Bank of Communication was reorganized and officially launched in 1986 after receiving clearance from both the Central Government and the State Council. It was the first commercial bank to be listed on the stock market in China. The formation of the Bank of Communications was not only significant because it resulted in the inclusion of one more bank, but also because it was a watershed moment that altered the dynamic of the financial sector ecosystem (Weihsuan, Arner, and Buckley, 2015). Since then, a large group of joint-stock commercial banks has emerged. After China's banking industry was completely opened to foreign investment in 2007, China's commercial banks began to place increased emphasis on enhancing their overall performance. Although the "catfish effect" brought about by the arrival of international banks assisted China's commercial banks in forming a perfect competition, it also brought about long-term impacts to China's banking industry (Tan and Floros, 2018); Then, the implementation of interest rate

liberalization has introduced additional intensity to the existing competition among banks (Chang, Liu, and Spiegel, 2015)

At the start of 2019, official China Securities Regulatory Commission revealed that as of the 30th of December in 2018, there were a total of 4,588 institutions functioning inside the Chinese banking industry (CBRC, 2019). Commercial banks listed on the Shanghai, Shenzhen, and Hong Kong stock markets total 48 as of this writing, such as the Hong Kong Transfers and Clearing Limited (HKECL) (HKSE). This demonstrates China's banking industry's extraordinary leap into a new era of competitiveness (CBRC, 2019). In the meantime, the safe, efficient, and stable operation of commercial banks was the key focus in the country's gradual improvement of its overall national strength and is an important part of the healthy development of the national economy (Danag, Wang and Yao, 2014). The degree of bank performance will not only effect the orderly development that takes place within the banks, but it will also affect the optimal distribution of social goods, the transmission of macro-economic factors and the durability of the market economic order (Qian, Zhang, and Liu, 2015). However, because of the long-term monopoly and government interference, In China's banking sector, there is a culture for low performance that is widespread and persistent. In general, commercial banks in China has done well in expanding their businesses. Banking's oligopolistic market structure and low market performance have come to the notice of intellectuals and business people together. Oligopolistic market creation and low relative market performance level of bank (Hou, Wang, and Zhang, 2014).

As China's economy continues its growth, the development of the banking industry directly influences the financial situation as well as socio-economic environments such as credit allocation for SMEs, financial inclusion, and poverty reduction. The financial services sector in China is currently through a period of change (Hsiao, Shen, and Bian, 2015). The Chinese banking system needs to implement necessary reforms in order to adapt and boost its development in order to be in an unbeatable position in a market that is extremely competitive (Nayak and Gao, 2018). Reforms will focus primarily on enhancing the efficiency of the banking system overall. In order to accomplish this goal, Chinese banks will need to determine the primary variables that influence their performance, and the regulatory body will have to conduct out industrial changes in responding to the features of these elements (Zhu and Chen, 2018). Therefore, this issue has great practical significance, not only for academia but also for the banking sector practitioners and regulators. The major goal of this study is to identify the elements that have the greatest impact on Chinese commercial banks' success. Before being used in this procedure, the CAMELS framework had been used to develop a model for checking the progress of Chinese commercial banks in China. Financial institutions' features, macroeconomic aspects, particularly financial considerations, and the banks' final performance were examined using a SEM technique. Results from this study were encouraging and give policymakers and practitioners a framework for analysing how government reforms inside the banking industry have affected the performance of Chinese banks. The remaining parts of the study are organized as described below. The review of the previous research can be found in Section 2. The approach and the data are discussed in Section 3. In part 4, the empirical findings are discussed, and in section 5, the findings are summarized together with any concluding notes.

2. Literature review

2.1 Camels Model

The CAMELS framework is a globally recognized rating system that is utilized by banking regulators to evaluate the soundness of financial institutions. Moreover, its CAMELS framework has indeed been extensively used in banking literature. For example, Muhmad and Hashim (2015) from 2008 to 2012, the CAMELS model was used to analyse the performance of Malaysian and foreign banks. This evaluation included the period of time from 2008 to 2012. As a consequence of this finding, it was determined that the most crucial elements in the success of Malaysian banking institutions are capital sufficiency, asset quality, profitability and liquidity. They believe that even though management efficiency did not show a major effect, It's probable that the research period's ratio for management efficiency isn't appropriate in the Malaysian banking sector. This is something that they believe despite the fact that management efficiency did not show a significant impact. They recommended that in future evaluations of bank performance, a different ratio should be used to determine the effectiveness of management. From 2000 to 2014, Saif-alyous, Saha, & Md-rus (2017) Analyzed Saudi Arabian international and domestic banks' professional competence using the CAMEL model In light of Saudi Arabia's banking reform, which benefits foreign banks and increases competition for Saudi Arabia's domestic banking industry, this assessment was made. According to the findings, high levels of non-performing loans in banks (NPL) performed the worst in comparison to those in other categories. When compared with the proportion of operating fees in domestic banks' total revenue, the proportion of operating fees in international banks' total revenue is adversely important with professional competence. During this time, an increase in lending activities had a strong positive effect on the business capacity of domestic banks, however a negative correlation was found between the increase in lending activities and the business capacity of foreign banks. There are numerous studies that use the CAMELS model to investigate the relationship between internal and external factors and bank performance. The econometric model was utilized by Adeusi, Kolapo, and Aluko (2014) in order to analysis of 14 nigerian banks between 2000 and 2013 will be carried out for this study. In addition to that, they obtained the internal variables of bank performance depending on the CAMEL parameters and employed the components of the macroeconomy as the external determinants. In both static and dynamic effect models, the rate of return (ROA) of financial institutions is significantly influenced by external factors such as asset values, managerial performance, and economic growth (ROA). Echekeba, Egbunike, and Ezu, (2014) also investigated the performance of the Commercial bank of Nigeria during 2010-2011 using the CAMEL model. They created a model using the common least squares method and employed CAMEL parameters as the independent variables in order to conduct an in-depth analysis of the impact that independent factors have on the ROA. Bank profitability is significantly affected by liquidity, but other four factors have little impact on the profitability for banks, according to this study's findings. It is therefore imperative for Nigerian financial institutions to maintain a reasonable liquidity position at all periods in terms of meeting their routine financial responsibilities. This will help to ensure that depositors continue to have faith in the banking industry while also increasing

profitability. Ishaq et al. (2016) used An examination of the financial results of 10 commercial banks operating in Pakistan between 2007 and 2013 was carried out in accordance with the CAMEL model utilising EPS as the dependent variable. The banks provided the data that was used in the study. According to the results of their investigation, the ratio of the bank's deposit equity, the ratio of its nonperforming loans (NPL), the ratio of its operating costs, and the ratio of its investment earnings to the performance of banks in Pakistan has a substantial and inverse relationship In addition, they discovered a connection between both the bank's assets ratio and its shareholders' capital, including its performance. According to the study, there was no correlation between the bank's performance and the amount of cash or interest income it generated. Nuhiu, Hoti, and Bektashi (2017) also investigated the impact that macroeconomic indicators and commercial bank-specific indicators have on banking performance. For the years 2010 to 2015, they analysed the financial data of 10 financial institutions in Kosovo and utilised it to obtain the mean rate of return (ROAE), ROAA and NIM of each company are included in this analysis. In addition to macroeconomic factors including such GDP growth and inflation, they also propose three analytical models that focus on the company's specific determinants (using CAMEL model), factors such as asset values, management efficiency, and liquidity can all have an impact on a bank's financial health. Their findings indicate that the success of commercial banks in Kosovo is primarily determined by the two most significant aspects of bank-specific metrics, which are efficient management and the quality of assets. The performance of commercial banks was significantly impacted by the two measures of capital adequacy ratio and liquidity. Asset quality, cost control, and liquidity, according to the research, are all potential contributors to an improvement inside the profitability of Kosovo's commercial banks.

2.2 Bank-Specific Factors and Bank Performance

Many studies have been done on the subject of internal communication and bank-specific characteristics, as well as the relationship between such elements and bank performance. Dawood (2014) conducted research to determine how the performance of the bank was affected by factors that were located within the bank itself. A selection of 23 banks in Pakistan operating between 2009 and 2012 was selected using an OLS analysis. Using ROA as a measure of performance allowed him to focus primarily on exploring the relationships between performance and factors such as bank cost-efficiency, liquidity, capital adequacy ratio, and deposit ratio and bank size. Research found that Pakistani commercial banks performed best when it came to efficiency, liquidity, and capital adequacy ratios. Overall performance of Pakistani financial institutions was unaffected by other factors, such as deposit ratios or bank sizes. The efficiency of 13 Jordanian commercial banks was examined by Alshatti (2014) in terms of the impact of internal financial metrics. The time-series data was analysed using the stationary test parameter of Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF). Later, the idea was put to the test with the help of regression analysis. Internal financial indicators influenced the profitability of 13 Jordanian commercial banks, as was also explored by Alshatti (2014a) Fast ratios with high liquid asset ratios increase the efficiency for Jordanian commercial banks, according to the conclusions of the study. This is the case regardless of whatever ratio is used. Therefore, Alshatti proposes that the managers of Jordanian commercial banks should devise a

standardized framework for liquidity management in order to guarantee that their operations would have sufficient liquidity. Frederick (2015) conducted research with the goal of identifying the elements that negatively impact the financial health of Uganda's corporate banks. His investigation covered all of the listed commercial banks in Uganda, and he conducted multiple linear regression analysis on the data obtained from these institutions between the years 2000 and 2011. His primary area of concentration is on the major internal drivers that are responsible for Uganda's local commercial banks achieving their desired levels of success. According to the findings of the study, the primary factors that determined the success of Uganda's domestic commercial banks in the period between 2000 and 2011 Managerial efficacy, asset quality, interest income, and the capital adequacy ratio were all considered. According to Daly and Frikha (2015), the primary factor that determines the performance of a bank is the amount of money deposited by customers and the size of the bank itself. They demonstrated this by doing data envelopment analysis (DEA) findings from an examination of the 2005-2009 performance of Bahrain's six conventional banks and its six Islamic banks (DEA). They take into account the internal and external characteristics of diversity and select the ROA, ROE, and Bank performance can be evaluated using metrics of efficiency. Islamic banks' ROE was impacted by a variety of factors, including bank size, asset loans, and market share, while traditional banks' ROA was positively influenced by share of the market, total assets, or net lending.

2.3 Macro-economic Factors and Bank Performance

The two most important macroeconomic variables examined in many studies looking into the relationship between macroeconomic indicators and bank performance are GDP and interest rates. To better understand the impact of macroeconomic factors on Malaysian commercial banks, Vejzagic and Zarafat (2014) conducted a study. They analysed data collected by banks between 1995 and 2011 to examine how the macroeconomy affects performance of institutions (as indicated by the average ROA). Growth in GDP, inflation and interest rates were among the macroeconomic factors that were taken account. They came to the conclusion that real GDP growth as well as real interest rates had a favorable impact on the profitability of banks. Growth in GDP has been found to have a strong association with bank profitability, according to the study. It's also worth noting in this article that while real interest rates have been demonstrated to have no effect on bank profitability, Malaysian researchers found that consumer price index (CPI) was the most relevant element at the time of the investigation. Kiganda (2014) utilized equity institutions in Kenya as a case study to explore the impact of macroeconomic variables on equity bank profitability. To examine how macro-factors like economic growth, inflation, as well as exchange rate affect the performance of Kenya's equity banks, he used annual data from 2008 to 2012. He then applied the production theory as a model, transformed this same Cobb-Douglas factor of production into a natural logarithm, and then applied ordinary least squares. The results showed that macroeconomic variables had little effect on profitability for Kenya's equity banks. As a result, he came to the conclusion that the amount of effectiveness achieved by equity banks in Kenya is, to a considerable extent, determined by internal metrics. The majority of research took into account both the internal bank-specific characteristics as well as the external macro-economic factors that influence bank performance simultaneously.

Chronopoulos et al. (2013) investigated the dynamic shifts that occurred between 1984 and 2010 in the overall performance and reliability of American commercial banks. They discovered that significant favorable effects on bank performance can be attributed to factors such as the bank's size, diversity, liquidity, and credit risk or asset growth. At the same time, they brought up the fact that bank earnings are cyclical and that bank performance has a propensity to improve during times of rapid economic expansion and a propensity to worsen during times of moderate economic expansion.

2.4 Financial Factors and Bank Performance

Financial factors, such as market concentration and market value, are examples of important aspects that contribute to the performance of banks. For example, in Căpraru and Ilnatov (2014), we analysed the most important elements determining the success of 143 banks in five countries in Central and Eastern Europe: Romanian, Hungary, the Czech Republic, Bulgaria, & Poland. The research covered the period from 2004 to 2011, and it focused on the years 2004 and 2011. ROA, ROE, and NIM are the indices that were used to measure the performance of the bank. They looked at a variety of characteristics, including those specific to banks and industries, as well as financial and macroeconomic factors. The crisis dummy variable is also presented in the paper at the same time. There is some evidence to imply that a bank's size has an adverse influence on all performance metrics, however the data supporting this claim is sparse. On performance measures, the ratio of costs to income is unfavourable. NIM is unaffected by credit risk, although ROE and ROA are greatly affected. The loan-to-deposit ratio does not have any relevance for any of the three dependent variables, while the capital adequacy ratio is having a beneficial influence on the performance of banks. The concentration of the market does not always have a compelling relevance, and the effects of credit risk and inflation are limited to ROA and ROE. The authors Guillén, Rengifo, and Ozsoz (2014) constructed a framework in order to describe and examine the determinants behind Latin American banking performance. They chose the performance of 200 different banks based on the microeconomic variables, and they used DEA analysis to do so. Berger's hypothesis on the RMP, SCP, and ES of data sets in the United States is supported by the findings of these researchers. The Structural Behavioural Performance (SBP) assumption is comprised of both the size (ES assumptions) and power (RMP) of the bank, which together determine the profitability of the bank. Petria, Capraru, and Ilnatov (2015) conducted a study in which they took into account a variety of financial aspects and discovered that doing so has an effect on the bank's overall performance. They examined the efficiency of the 27 banks that were members of the European Union during the years of 2004 and 2011. They further classified the elements that influence the profitability of banks into three categories: bank-specific, macroeconomic and financial factors. As a result of their findings, they urge that banking authorities in EU countries tighten their oversight of banks' credit risk through increased competition (market concentration).

According to what has been noticed in the research literature, ROA and ROE are often measured in the majority of prior studies to evaluate the performance of the bank. However, in light of the criticisms that have been leveled against the efficacy of these two measures (due to

the fact that they only concentrate on maximizing profits and ignore other factors that have a significant impact; Mourhij, 2017) Bank risk must be considered and risk-based metrics developed for evaluating bank performance. Therefore, present research differs from the previous studies in that, a PI is developed using CAMELS indicators and after evaluating the performance of the banks the effect of both internal and external variables is analysed to give a clearer picture of significant determinants on banking performance. Finally, very few, if any studies employed this methodology in the context of China so this research can bridge the existing gap in the literature.

3. Research Method

3.1 Sample and Data

A total of 48 commercial banks in China are included on the SHSE, SZSE, and HKSE as the research population only 14 banks were performing for 10 years research period i.e., 2009 to 2018. When compared to the established countries of the west, the banking industry in China has had a comparatively short amount of time to develop (Chen, Matousek, and Wanke, 2018). The majority of commercial banks have only recently been listed, and their listing periods are often quite brief. In light of these circumstances, this investigation makes use of purposive sampling in order to pick the list commercial banks that were operational throughout the time period under investigation. The collection of sample banks is shown below in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Sample Banks.

Banks	Code	Institutional Type
Industrial and Commercial Bank of China Limited	ICBC	Large state-owned
Bank of China Limited	BOC	Large state-owned
China Construction Bank Corporation	CCB	Large state-owned
Bank of Communications Co., Ltd.	BCM	Large state-owned
China Citic Bank Corporation Limited	CCBC	Joint-stock commercial bank
China Merchants Bank Co., Ltd.	CMB	Joint-stock commercial bank
Shanghai Pudong Development Bank Co., Ltd.	SPDB	Joint-stock commercial bank
China Minsheng Banking Corp., Ltd.	CMBC	Joint-stock commercial bank
Hua Xia Bank Co., Ltd.	HXBC	Joint-stock commercial bank
Ping An Bank Co., Ltd.	PIBC	Joint-stock commercial bank
Industrial Bank Co., Ltd.	IBC	Joint-stock commercial bank
Bank of Beijing Co., Ltd.	BOBJ	City commercial bank
Bank of Nanjing Co., Ltd.	BONJ	City commercial bank
Bank of Ningbo Co., Ltd	BONB	City commercial bank

This research makes use of secondary data by accessing financial reports and data that were publicly revealed by banks in 2009-2018 on their government sites; the annual stock data of the banks was collected from the SHSE, SZSE, and HKSE; and macro-economic variables were collected from the database of the World Bank.

3.2 Estimation Technique

In terms of the empirical analysis, this study began by developing a financial performance evaluating model by making use of the CAMELS parameters. Next, the researchers evaluated the performance of each bank. Profitability, capital adequacy, efficiency, liquidity, asset quality, and risk sensitivity all add to a bank's financial performance, according to the CAMELS framework. A financial performance measuring index based on these parameters is being developed for the purpose of assessing the bank's efficiency in the current examination. A large portion of this index is divided into the following four tasks:

In the first step of the CAMELS algorithm, a weight is determined for each parameter. The significance of each criterion, in addition to the bank's earnings, serves as the foundation for the weight allocation principle. For instance, as according Reddy (2012), In the long run, the success or failure of a bank is determined by all of these variables. As a result, each of these criteria should be given a higher weight, but the weight given to management or liquidity should be reduced relative to the weight given to these elements because excessive liquidity reduces bank efficiency. The proportions of CAMELS parameters and variables are determined based on Rashid, Khaleequzzaman, and Jabeen's (2015) research and are presented in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Overview of weight allocation for parameters (Source: Reddy, 2012).

Performance parameters	Composite weights	Performance factors	Weights
Capital adequacy	20%	Capital adequacy ratio	50%
		Coverage ratio	50%
Asset quality	20%	NPL/ loans	100%
Management efficiency	10%	Profit per branch	20%
		Profit per employee	40%
		Noninterest Inc./noninterest exp.	40%
Earning	20%	Return on assets (ROA)	50%
		Return on equity (ROE)	30%
		Net interest Inc./ loans	20%
Liquidity	10%	Net loan/ total assets	50%
		Liquid assets/total assets	50%
Sensitivity to risk	20%	Market risk	100%

Second, the values for each bank are standardized. The standardized calculation formula is as follows:

$$S_{ikt} = [(\beta_{ikt} - \mu_{kt}) / \sigma_{kt}]$$

If you want to know what's going on in the CAMELS model, you'll need to know what's going on in bank I at the time of the CAMELS model's kth factor. To arrive at an accurate financial assessment, the CAMELS investment evaluation method takes into consideration a number of variables, each with its own distinct characteristics, dimensions, and magnitudes. For future computations and analysis, it each component's raw data must be normalized and erase the

unit's restriction by converting data into dimensionless pure numbers. To ensure the validity of the results, this is done.

The third step was to create a formula to integrate the standards of the different CAMELS variables, following Teker (2011). The following are the precise calculations in each of the bank's CAMELS parameters:

Capital Adequacy: $CA_{it} = W_{1it} S_{1it} + W_{2it} S_{2it}$

Asset Quality: $AQ_{it} = W_{1it} S_{1it}$

Management Efficiency: $ME_{it} = W_{1it} S_{1it} + W_{2it} S_{2it}$

Earnings: $ES_{it} = W_{1it} S_{1it} + W_{2it} S_{2it} + W_{3it} S_{3it}$

Liquidity: $LY_{it} = W_{1it} S_{1it} + W_{2it} S_{2it}$

Sensitivity to Risk: $SR_{it} = W_{1it} S_{1it}$

Bank i's CAMELS parameter factor, S_{it} , at time t; W_{it} is the established value of each bank's factor at any given time, S_{it} .

Annual financial results index is computed as a weighted sum of capital sufficiency, capital adequacy, management efficiency and earnings as well as liquidity and risk sensitivity. The following is a breakdown of the PI's calculation:

$PI_{it} = \alpha_{k1} CA_{it} + \alpha_{k2} AQ_{it} + \alpha_{k3} ME_{it} + \alpha_{k4} ES_{it} + \alpha_{k5} LY_{it} + \alpha_{k6} SR_{it}$

Where α_k is the predetermined parameter k gravity, CA_{it} , AQ_{it} , ME_{it} , ES_{it} , LY_{it} , SR_{it} are the values of the CAMELS parameters of bank i at time t.

It is necessary to look at the relationship between bank performance and three different sorts of influencing elements in the second phase of the empirical investigation.

$PI_{it} = f \{ \text{bank-specific indicators, financial indicators, macroeconomic indicators} \}$

In this paper, we used AMOS 23.0 to do structural equation modelling (SEM) on the data, which included bank size (BSZ), reserve (RES), overheads ratios (VER), deposits ratio (DPR), or operational efficiency (OPE).

3.3 Variable Definition

3.3.1 Bank performance

The CAMELS parameters are used to create the bank's performance index as the dependant variable. Using the CAMELS performance index, a bank's capital adequacy ratio; asset quality; managerial efficiency; earnings; liquidity; and risk sensitivity are all assessed.

3.3.2 Bank-Specific Indicators

a. Bank Size (BSZ)

The size of the bank is an independent variable in this investigation. A measure of a bank's size based on past research involves taking equal natural logarithm of its total assets:

$$\text{Bank Size (BSZ)} = [\ln (\text{total bank assets})]$$

b. Reserves (RES)

Commercial banks deposit their reserves in China's central bank. Deposit reserve is used as an independent variable in this article, and its natural logarithm is used to measure the variable's value as follows:

$$\text{Reserves (RES)} = [\ln (\text{Reserves})]$$

c. Overheads Ratio (OVR)

The banking industry's operating costs are reflected in this ratio. A bank's profitability is often higher if its overheads ratio is lower.

$$\text{Overheads Ratio (OVR)} = [\text{Overheads} / \text{Total assets}]$$

d. Deposits Ratio (DPR)

In this study, this variable is referred to as:

$$\text{Deposits Ratio (DPR)} = [\text{Deposits} / \text{Equity}]$$

e. Operating Efficiency (OPE)

Interest earned is the bank's primary source of revenue, hence operating expenses or interest income are used to calculate the bank's operational efficiency:

$$\text{Operating Efficiency (OPE)} = [\text{Operating expense} / \text{Net interest income}]$$

3.3.3 Financial Indicators

a. Market Value

The total market value is equal to the number of outstanding shares times the price per share, as determined by the publicly traded commercial banks.

$$\text{Market Value (MKV)} = [\text{Price per share} \times \text{Number of shares}]$$

Due to the ever-changing market, this article relies on the stock price and share count published by SHSE, SZSE, and HKSE on the year's final trading day.

3.3.4 Macroeconomic Indicators

a. Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

A country's GDP is an important indicator of its overall economic well-being, and it is used to measure the national economic status (Feldstein, 2017). A number of previous research,

including those by Bulman, Kolkma, and Kraay (2016), Bank profitability and performance are positively affected by GDP, according to research.

b. Real Interest Rate (RIR)

Real interest rates are referred to as the interest rate received by depositors and investors after inflation is taken into consideration. As long as prices and the value of money don't change, it's a measure of how much interest will accrue (Rachel and Smith, 2015). It is also the long-term amount of money that is reflected in the rate of interest (Lisack, Sajedi, and Thwaites, 2017). Another macroeconomic statistic used in this study is the real interest rate.

4. Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Summary of statistics

Table 3 provides general bank information for 14 commercial banks operating as of 2018, such branch locations, bank staff, and total assets. ICBC, CCB, and BOC are the three largest banks in China, which may be related to the fact that they had been govt banks prior to the 2003 reforming of China's banking sector.

Table 3: Bank information.

Bank	Total branch	Total employees	Total assets (million RMB)
PIBC	1079	25847	3,248,474
BONV	317	12317	1,032,042
SPDE	1799	52319	6,137,240
HXBC	968	42353	2,508,927
CMBC	2964	55265	5,902,086
CMB	1830	72530	6,297,638
BONB	182	9378	1,141,162
IBC	2064	58997	6,416,842
BOBJ	561	14680	2,329,805
BCM	3270	88906	9,038,254
ICBC	16888	453048	26,087,043
CCB	14920	352621	22,124,383
BOC	11605	311133	19,467,424
CCBC	1435	56724	5,677,691

Table 4 shows the performance index and the average value of 14 listed China's commercial banks from 2008 to 2018; larger PI value reflects better bank performance.

Table 4: Bank PI statistics.

Bank	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Composite PI
PIBC	-0.933	-0.426	-0.599	-0.607	-0.647	-0.526	-0.789	-0.711	-0.248	-0.333	-0.581893
BONB	-0.052	-0.465	-0.347	-0.169	-0.001	-0.321	-0.762	-0.605	-0.250	-0.382	-0.335355
SPDB	0.291	0.134	-0.032	0.007	-0.042	0.010	0.091	0.209	0.029	0.388	0.108514
HXBC	-0.153	-0.173	-0.165	-0.196	-0.081	-0.287	-0.043	-0.079	-0.053	-0.049	-0.127972
CMBC	-0.252	-0.074	-0.152	0.230	0.146	0.168	0.144	-0.063	-0.299	-0.094	-0.024666
CMB	0.391	0.171	0.175	0.323	0.249	0.158	0.239	0.308	0.510	0.890	0.341423
BONB	0.492	0.447	0.278	0.350	0.347	-0.061	-0.022	0.165	0.340	0.098	0.243475
IBC	0.152	0.234	0.228	0.004	-0.076	0.204	0.217	0.248	0.004	0.101	0.131680
BOBJ	0.561	0.466	0.224	0.029	0.454	0.463	-0.259	-0.054	-0.309	-0.261	0.131406
BCM	-0.092	-0.016	0.048	-0.137	-0.120	-0.023	0.137	0.041	-0.055	-0.242	-0.045768
ICBC	-0.260	-0.074	0.072	0.001	-0.120	-0.066	0.156	0.172	-0.044	-0.062	-0.022441
CCB	0.024	0.205	0.257	0.326	0.272	0.268	0.568	0.554	0.325	0.154	0.295160
BOC	-0.155	-0.124	-0.170	-0.193	-0.276	-0.185	0.042	0.011	0.048	-0.130	-0.113134
CCBC	-0.015	-0.306	0.183	0.034	-0.106	0.198	0.281	-0.197	0.001	-0.078	-0.000430

According to the table, only six commercial banks out of 14 have a PI mean higher than zero; three of these are CMB (CCB), BONB (BONB), and CMB (MBB). As of 2018, CMB's average PI is 0.3414, whereas the average yearly PI value is larger than zero, at 0.8901. Two of the worst performers in the field are BONB and PIBC PIBC has the lowest PI (-0.5819), with 2009 being the worst year for the company (-0.933). Chi and Li (2017) also pointed out that China's listed banks have poor overall performance, which they attribute to a lack of managerial efficiency, as can be observed.

Table 5 both minimum and maximum values, as well as other descriptive statistics, are provided for the sample variables, as well as the standard deviation values. According to the table, there is a wide range between the highest or minimum of bank size, sustainability efforts, and market value, which demonstrates the wide range of Chinese banks.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics.

Variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
Bank Size (RMB)	140	13.847	17.0769	15.9421	6.0131
Reserves (RMB)	140	10.34	13.57	12.435	8.7534
Overheads Ratio	140	0.0076	0.0233	0.0143	0.0029
Deposit Ratio	140	5.5535	22.7280	11.2369	2.9878
Operating Efficiency Ratio	140	0.3253	1.0593	0.6622	0.1349
Market Value (RMB)	140	12.46	15.69	14.555	3.1637
GDP (RMB)	140	3.1924	8.2075	5.5874	1.6001
Real Interest Rate	140	-2.33	5.45	2.024	2.7315
PI	140	-0.9327	0.8896	0.0235	0.2968

4.2 Constructs and Structural Equation Model

A structural equation model was implemented in AMOS 23.0, and the hypotheses were verified. Figure 1 shows the final model after a lot of testing and troubleshooting.

Figure 1: Modified Model

The model fit indices are shown in table 6:

Table 6: Model fit indices.

Variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
Bank Size (RMB)	140	13.847	17.0769	15.9421	6.0131
Reserves (RMB)	140	10.34	13.57	12.435	8.7534
Overheads Ratio	140	0.0076	0.0233	0.0143	0.0029
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PI	140	-0.9327	0.8896	0.0235	0.2968

CMIN represents the degree to which the variables correlation matrix as well as the real data correlation matrix are in agreement. The less significant the distinction between the 2 correlation matrices (P 0.05) is when the CMIN is less. CMIN = 0 indicates that hypothesis model and the actual data are 100% consistent. When the number of variables or data are too large, CMIN suffers from a poor fit between both the theoretical model as well as the actual data. As a result, AMOS adds CMIN/DF as a new indicator for evaluating model fit in order to reduce the influence between variables on sample counts. As a general rule, a model fitness of

1CMIN/CF3 can be acceptable (Mueller and Hancock, 2018). Using the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), an indicator of model fit with respect to actual data, the more closely GFI gets to 1, the better this same model fits the data (Lee, Kim, and Kim, 2016). Adjusted GFI (AGFI) represents a GFI that is not affected by degrees of freedom. GFI is used as the inspection standard. A model fitness index (AGFI) of 0.9 or more indicates a satisfactory fit (Lee, Kim, and Kim, 2016). A value of 0.9 or above indicates that the hypothesis parameter is well-fitted to the data (Mueller and Hancock, 2018). The RMSEA value is somewhat higher than 0.05, indicating that this index is within a reasonable range for most applications and studies.

Table 7: Regression Weights.

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
OPE <--- Specific	1.000			
DPR <--- Specific	-1.626	.344	-4.730	***
OVR <--- Specific	-0.005	.212	-.023	.982
RES <--- Specific	.284	.093	3.067	.002
BSZ <--- Specific	.309	.084	3.683	***
RIR <--- Macro-economic	12.629	5.727	2.205	.027
PI <--- Specific	5.593	2.808	1.992	.046
PI <--- Macro-economic	-29.724	14.223	-2.090	.037
PI <--- MKV	1.246	.730	1.706	.088
GDP <--- Macro-economic	1.000			

Table 8: Standardized Regression Weights.

	Estimate
OPE <--- Specific	.437
DPR <--- Specific	-.689
OVR <--- Specific	-.002
RES <--- Specific	.327
BSZ <--- Specific	.421
RIR <--- Macro-economic	.239
PI <--- Specific	.929
PI <--- Macro-economic	-.843
PI <--- MKV	.138
GDP <--- Macro-economic	1.000

In Table 7 and Table 8, regression weights, the bank-specific and macroeconomic factors have a P-value of 0.046, respectively, indicating that banking performance is greatly affected by their actions, while MKV has a P-value of 0.088, which indicates that MKV does not even have a significant correlation with performance of the banks.

Specific > Macro-economic > MKV (financial) components have the impact on the performance of the bank, as seen in the above table. Furthermore, overall standard regression weight for bank-specific variables is 0.929, showing that PI is positively impacted by bank-specific characteristics. PI is negatively impacted by macroeconomic circumstances, as evidenced by the -0.843 standard regression weight.

There is a 0.982 significance level for OVR, which indicates that OVR has no meaningful impact on PI, but the other four components all meet the 0.05 significance threshold for the bank-specific variables. This is based on the rankings above: DPR > OPE > Bsz > Res > Ovr > PI > Ranking of factors on PI: DPR > OPE > Bsz > RES > OVR. Both variables were significant in the macroeconomic dimension, and the order of effect degrees was GDP>RIR, with a negative influence direction, passing a significance level of 0.05.

5. Conclusions

China's progress as well as the current status stability of a country's banking system were taken into consideration when developing the research model & conducting an empirical analysis of 14 publicly listed commercial banks over a ten-year period. Bank-specific factors were found to positively influence bank performance which is consistent with Rashid, Khaleequzzaman, and Jabeen (2015), Bagntasarian and Mamatzakis (2018), and Fukuyama and Matousek (2017). The bank's sensitivity to danger is taken into consideration while calculating PI in this article, which is why the banking reserve does have a positive link to PI. The market valuation of a bank was not known to have a significant correlation with the banks' performance as measured by financial criteria. It's possible it is possible that stock market volatility, which can be influenced by the market, industrial, political, or currency or exchange rate changes, may have a role in this relationship. This result is in contrast with previous research (exp. Căpraru and Ihnatov, 2014). Recent studies have revealed that macroeconomic conditions negatively affect bank performance (ex. Safrali and Gumus, 2010)

Researchers found that Chinese commercial banks' performance is heavily influenced by bank-specific characteristics. Consequently, it is advised that commercial banks throughout China improve the efficiency of their internal operations. Furthermore, risk management has become increasingly vital to bank operations and management as a result of globalisation and the current financial climate (Lundqvist and Vilhelmsson, 2016). It is therefore vital that Chinese banks put in place a risk response control scheme, which is a fundamental factor of sustained bank performance growth.

In addition, a financial order necessitates an increase in regulatory actions. It is imperative that the amount of economic oversight be closely linked to a well-functioning legal system (Zhang et al., 2016). When financial regulations are excessively stringent, commercial banks will be limited in their business scope and operating performance, therefore the government is paying attention to market economy rules.

Chinese commercial banks are few, operate for a short period of time, as well as the banking information disclosure system isn't ideal compared to those in the West. Therefore, only 14

banks which have operated on the New York Stock Exchange for more than a decade have been included in this analysis. This means that future studies can look at using a larger sample that includes people from a broader range of geographical locations. Utilize a longer time span of bank data to broaden the scope of the study's findings.

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization: Babak Naysary, Liao Yunhan; Data curation: Liao Yunhan; Formal analysis: Liao Yunhan and Babak Naysary; Investigation: Liao Yunhan and Babak Naysary; Methodology: Babak Naysary and Liao Yunhan; Project administration: Babak Naysary, Salaar Farooq and Liao Yunhan; Resources: Liao Yunhan; Software: Liao Yunhan; Supervision: Babak Naysary; Validation: Babak Naysary and Salaar Farooq; Writing – original draft: Liao Yunhan and Babak Naysary; Writing – review & editing: Babak Naysary and Salaar Farooq

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